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THE SIGNIFICANCE OF BABUR'S SCIENTIFIC AND SPIRITUAL HERITAGE TODAY

Makhmudova Khurmat Mukhtorovna
Student of Bukhara State University
Department of Education of Jurisprudence
Thurmat156@gmail.com

ANNOTATSIYA: *Ushbu maqolada Zahiriddin Muhammad Boburning hayoti va ijodi, Bobur barcha temuriy shahzodalar kabi maxsus tarbiyachilar, yirik fozilu ulamolar ustozligida harbiy ta'lim, fiqh ilmi, arab va fors tillarini o'rganishi, ko'plab tarixiy va adabiy asarlar mutolaa qilishi, ilm-fanga, she'riyatga qiziqishi yuqoriligi haqida, Amir Temur davlatining poytaxti, strategik va geografik jihatdan muhim bo'lgan Samarqandni egallash va Movarounnahrda markazlashgan kuchli davlatni saqlashqa qaratilgan harakatlari va Shimoliy Hindistonning Bengaliyagacha bo'lgan qismini o'ziga bo'ysundirgani, davlat boshqaruvi sohasida katta islohotlarni amalga oshirgani, uning ilmiy-ma'naviy merosining bugungi kundagi ahamiyati, Boburning asarlari va u haqida yozilgan asarlar tahlili, bugungi kunda Bobur merosining o'rganishning ahamiyati, tafakkur yuritmoq, yangicha fikrlamoq uchun albatta o'tmishni bilish zarurati to'g'risidagi fikr-muhazalar bayon qilinadi.*

TAYANCH SO'ZLAR: *Temuriylar, "Bobur" ("Sher"), Andijon, Samarqand, Kobul, Dehli, "Boburnoma", "Mubayyin", "Aruz risolasi", "Risolai volidiyya", "Mubayyin", "Yo'lbars na'rasi"*

АННОТАЦИЯ: *В данной статье рассказывается о жизни и творчестве Захириддина Мухаммада Бабур, как и все Тимурские князья, Бабур изучал военное образование, юриспруденцию, арабский и персидский языки под опекой специальных учителей, великих добродетельных ученых, прочитал множество исторических и литературных произведений, наука - о его высоком интересе к науке и поэзии, Действия Амира Тимура были направлены на захват Самарканда, столицы государства, имеющего стратегически и географическое значение, и сохранение сильного государства с центром в Моваруннахре, а также подчинение северной части Индии до Бенгалии, проведение крупных реформ в области общественного устройства администрация, Будет сделана важность его научного и духовного наследия сегодня, анализ произведений Бабур и произведений, написанных о нем, важность изучения наследия Бабур сегодня, необходимость познания прошлого, чтобы мыслить и мыслить по-новому.*

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА: *Тимуриды, «Бабур» («Лев»), Андижан, Самарканд, Кабул, Дели, «Бобурнома», «Мубайин», «Аруз Рисола», «Рисолай Волидия», «Мубайин», «Рев тигра».*

ABSTRACT: This article tells about the life and work of Zakhiriddin Muhammad Babur, like all Timur princes, Babur studied military education, jurisprudence, Arabic and Persian languages under the tutelage of special teachers, great virtuous scholars, and read many historical and literary works, science - about his high interest in science and poetry, Amir Timur's actions were aimed at capturing Samarkand, the capital of a state of strategic and geographical importance, and maintaining a strong state centered in Movarunnahr, as well as subjugating the northern part of India up to Bengal, carrying out major reforms in the field of social structure administration, The importance of his scientific and spiritual heritage today, the analysis of Babur's works and works written about him, the importance of studying Babur's legacy today, the need to know the past in order to think and think in a new way will be made.

KEY WORDS: Timurids, "Babur" ("Lion"), Andijan, Samarkand, Kabul, Delhi, "Boburnoma", "Mubain", "Aruz Risola", "Risolai Volidiya", "Mubayin", "Roar of the Tiger".

"Among the kings of Asia in terms of generosity and bravery, talent, love of science and art, and successful practice of them
No king can be found equal to Babur".
William Erskine, translator of "Boburnoma".

INTRODUCTION.

Before talking about the significance of Babur's scientific and spiritual heritage today, it is permissible to dwell on Babur's life. Because Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur is a descendant of the Timurids and the founder of the great Babiri dynasty.

Babur (pseudonym; full name Zahiriddin Muhammad ibn Umarshaikh Mirza) on February 14, 1483 in Andijan is a major representative of Uzbek classical literature: a great poet; historian, geographer; a statesman, a talented general; the founder of the Baburi dynasty, the Timurid prince.

Babur's father - Umarshaikh Mirza was the governor of Fergana region, his mother - Qutlugh Nigorkhanim was the daughter of Khan of Mongolia and Tashkent governor Yunus Khan. Babur's mother was an educated and intelligent woman who actively supported Babur in his administration and accompanied him in his military campaigns. Umarshaikh Mirza's family lived in the arch of Andijan, the capital city. The mayor spent the summer months on the banks of the Sirdarya River, in Akhsi, and the rest of the year in Andijan.

Babur spent his youth in Andijan. Babur, like all Timurid princes, studied military education, jurisprudence, Arabic and Persian languages under the tutelage of special tutors, great virtuous scholars, read many historical and literary works, became

interested in science and poetry. Because of his courage and bravery, he received the nickname “Babur” (“Lion”) from his youth.

Following his father’s path, Babur devotes himself to the famous Sufi Khwaja Ahror and grows up in the spirit of his sect, remaining faithful to this belief until the end of his life. Later, in the work “Baburnoma”, Babur Khwaja Ahror’s spirit repeatedly saved him from inevitable destruction, illness and helplessness, and pointed out that he guided him in the most difficult conditions. After his father’s premature death in Akhsi, at the age of 39, the eldest son of the family, 12-year-old Babur, ascended the throne in June 1494.

Babur’s initial political goal was to capture the strategically and geographically important Samarkand, the capital of Amir Temur’s state, and to maintain and strengthen a strong state centered in Movarunnahr and restore Amir Temur’s kingdom.

Babur makes two unsuccessful campaigns to Samarkand. Babur faced great difficulties in providing the army. Some of the servants flee to Andijan and Akhsi. After that, some begs who remained in Andijan turned their backs on Babur and went to his brother Jahangir Mirza’s side. In 1500, Sultan Ali Mirza secretly surrendered Samarkand to Shaibani Khan without a fight. However, a certain part of the city’s inhabitants and nobles were in favor of the restoration of Timurid rule. They sent a letter to the governor of Fergana, Babur, and invited him to occupy Samarkand.

When Babur arrived in Samarkand with his army (240 people) in the late autumn of 1500, the people greeted him and opened the city gates. Shaibani Khan’s 600 soldiers left to protect the city will be destroyed. Shaibani Khan retreats to Bukhara. In a short time, all districts of Samarkand, the cities of Karshi and Guzor will recognize Babur’s governorship. But the city ran out of food supplies and famine began. When Shaibani Khan learned about this, he gathered a lot of strength and started marching to Samarkand again. In April 1501, Babur’s troops were defeated in a battle near the village of Saripul on the banks of Zarafshan. Babur retreats to Samarkand. The city was again besieged and it lasted for four months. The inhabitants of the besieged city were starving, and in the second half of 1501, Babur left Samarkand out of desperation and went to Tashkent, to Mahmud Khan. But all their campaigns fail. After that, Babur with 200-300 soldiers passed through the Hissar mountains to Afghanistan and took advantage of the internal strife there to capture Ghazni and Kabul. After Babur captured Kabul, he began to build an independent state, organized the army, and established strict internal discipline. Babur treated Kabul and Afghanistan in general as his own country, started construction, beautification, development of professions and agriculture. He established rest camps such as “Bogi Shahrora”, “Bogi Jahonoro”, “Ortabog”, “Bogi Wafa” and “Bogi Babur”.

On November 24, 1512, Babur was again defeated by the Shaybanites in the battle of Gijduvan and was forced to return to Kabul. Babur immediately gave up hope of capturing Mowaroonnahr and turned his attention to India. By the spring of 1519, Babur began to implement plans to conquer India and organized several campaigns over the next 5-6 years. Finally, in April 1526, in Panipat, he crushed the army of 100,000 people of his main rival, the Sultan of Delhi, Ibrahim Lodi, with 12,000 soldiers and captured Delhi. Soon after, he won over the second largest Indian warlord, Rano Sango, and subjugated the northern part of India up to Bengal. Babur, who chose Agra as his capital, began large-scale construction and improvement works. In this way, Babur founded the powerful Babur dynasty, which ruled India for about three and a half centuries.

Babur died at the age of 47 in Agra, the capital of the kingdom he founded, and was buried there, and later in 1539, according to his will, the hoki was brought to Kabul and placed in the “Garden of Babur” that he built.

BABUR’S LITERARY HERITAGE.

Babur was well aware of the past, literature and history, music and art, devoted to religious teachings, Babur was always in the circle of scholars and virtues, especially the people of creativity, professions and crafts. rgazib sponsored them, encouraged them materially and spiritually. Such loving attitude towards people of creativity and art was not in vain. Babur was creative by nature. From his youth to the end of his life, he was engaged in effective creative work, he did not stop his creativity in any conditions and situations, as a result, he left a rich scientific and literary legacy. Babur started writing rubai and ghazals at the age of 18-19. His ghazal “Topmadim” with radium and his rubai beginning with the verse “Yod etmas emish kishini ghurbatda kishi” are related to his life in those years. Babur’s poetic works were collected and made into a divan. Currently, his 119 ghazals, one masnu poem, 209 rubai’s, more than 10 optical holes and verses, more than 50 problems and more than 60 fards have been identified. There are also 8 masnavis with a total size of 270 bytes.

Babur concludes his scientific treatise on one of the main issues of Eastern poetry, aruz weight, its theory and practice. In 1518-19, he started his creative work on the royal work “Baburnoma”, which made the name of Babur famous in the world. In addition to the above-mentioned works of Babur, there were also a number of treatises specially devoted to the art of music and military affairs. But the text of the next two works has not yet been found. In “Hatti Baburiy”, the author edited the Arabic alphabet and adapted it to the criteria of the Turkish language and pronunciation in order to simplify and facilitate the writing.

According to the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in 1993, the 510th anniversary of Babur's birth was solemnly celebrated, and wide opportunities were given to study and research the scientific and spiritual heritage of Babur's work.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY.

From Babur to us, a great scientific and spiritual heritage has been left in the fields of state administration, literature and history, music and art, and a number of other fields. Although some of the centuries have not been found and have not reached us completely, it is important to educate the young generation, who are growing up as a spiritually mature person in all aspects, by deeply studying and analyzing the works that have reached us.

In this article, methods such as comparison of data and materials, study of documents, analysis of statistical data, making proposals for the integration of the obtained necessary resources with the present day have been widely used.

The International Babur Foundation, founded on December 23, 1993 and headed by naturalist scientist Zakirjon Mashrabov from Andijan, has done great work in the study of Babur's work. The foundation's scientific expedition organized scientific trips by car to more than 10 Eastern countries, covered more than 200 thousand km, collected new information about the sites of Babur and the Baburites, their scientific heritage, and used them for scientific purposes. entered the property. Based on this information, more than 10 scientific, documentary, artistic works (Z. Mashrabov, S. Shokarimov: "Babur who spanned the ages"; S. Jalilov: "Babur's state of Ferghana", "Babur and Andijan"; Kamchibek Junior: "Indian yellow"; H. Sultanov: "Babur's dreams", "Baburiynama"; R. Shamsuddinov: "In the footsteps of the Baburis", "Baburii dynasty"; T. Nizam: "Three words", about 10 documentaries and video films (F. Rasulov: "Izidan Babur", "Holy Steps"; T. Roziyev: "Salute to Babur", "International scientific expedition named after Babur"; T. Hamidov: "Iftikhar", etc.) were created. the works gained great importance for the study of Babur's life and work.

Babur and to understand him more deeply are going on consistently. During the study of Babur's scientific and spiritual heritage, new discoveries can always be made.

In order to understand Babur better, Babur's works should be inculcated in the minds of the young generation from childhood. To understand and explain Babur, it is necessary to love and be loved. In my opinion, Babur's works have a great role in forming love for the Motherland and the nation in the hearts of the young generation.

Not only Babur's work, but also his rich life is an example for the younger generation. His creativity, patriotism, truthfulness should be an example for all of us. Babur's work encourages us all to awareness, goodness, and humility.

Babur's scientific and spiritual heritage today, we got acquainted with many articles and documents written about Babur, his works, and his life. In this process, we were once again convinced that Babur as a person was a highly spiritual person, and as a king, he was just and philanthropic.

RESULTS.

A careful comparison of data and materials, Babur was once again made to study documents. Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur is one of the great people who had a great influence on the entire Asian civilization. As fate would have it, he occupied Afghanistan first, and then India, making a turning point in the historical development of these countries. Jawaharlal Nehru, the great child of the Indian people, says about this: "With the arrival of Babur, India became a powerful kingdom under the rule of a new dynasty. Therefore, the threat or probability of European attack has dropped to a level that is non-existent".

Both his parents and his grandmother paid special attention to the child's growth and upbringing, including his physical education. As a result, Babur grew up to be a brave young man. As the heir to the throne, he was trained in military affairs from a young age, and with the help of special teachers, they supervised his perfect learning of Arabic and Persian languages. He was taught to recite the Qur'an from an early age. As their faith grew stronger, they taught the laws of jurisprudence, history and Eastern literature. Babur grew up to be uninterested in the fleeting pleasures of everyday life, and he did not indulge in food and drink. Since childhood, he has been thinking about what is good and what is bad in life. He treated his friends and peers equally, regardless of their lineage. He never got used to ambition and pride. He did not lie, did not complain, and grew up to be kind-hearted. Babur is brought up to be smarter, more alert, wiser and wiser than others. He was distinguished from others by his good looks, spiritual freshness, intelligence and fine taste. Later, during the royal years, he did not indulge in excessive wealth, he did not indulge in the feeling of enjoying ornaments, he was accustomed to look at them with disdain. Such behavior can be observed throughout his life and in his state activities.

So, Babur was devoted to books and science from a young age. The main reason for this is the environment. Nowadays, if a parent can't look up from the phone, do they tell the child to read a book? Not at all. Because there is a saying in our people that "A bird does what it sees in its nest". This is primarily based on the example of parents.

"Boburnoma", which has received a worthy place in the treasury of world culture and has been translated into many languages, is studied as an important historical work,

and is still a source of discoveries for various fields of science. This work is particularly important in terms of researching mathematical numbers represented by letters. Boburnama is an important and unique monument in world literature and source studies; the first prose memoir and historical-scientific work in Uzbek literature. Author: Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur. It was written in the old Uzbek (Chigatai) language (about 1518/1519-1530). It is also known by such names as “Baburiya”, “Voqeoti Babur”, “Voqeanoma”, “Tuzuki Boburi”, “Tabaqoti Boburi”, “Tavorikhi Boburi”. Babur himself used the names “Vaqoye” and “Tarikh”. The historical and political events that took place in Central Asia, Afghanistan, and India in the years 1494-1529 are described with great accuracy in Baburnama, which are directly related to the author’s life and political activity.

In the history of our literature, no word artist has avoided the poetic art of “history”. Zahiruddin Muhammad Babur also paid serious attention to these art examples. In classical poetry, important historical events are expressed in special words and phrases. This art is based on a mathematical calculation called abjad. Our grandfather Alisher Navoi says about Abjad:

My mind is the master of all the wise,

There was a school for children in the education of love alphabet.

That is, the mind, which is the teacher of all people of intelligence and wisdom, became like a young child in the education of love alphabet.

There are some important historical indicators and dates in Baburnama, about which the author did not limit himself to the details of years and events, but used poetic lines or special expressions related to this historical reality. In such words and phrases, the reality finds its historical expression in the calculation of abjad, that is, when the letters of the words are converted into numbers.

Expressing the value of numbers with letters is called abjad and jimal calculation. “Abjad” is the collective name for eight words containing all 28 letters of the Arabic alphabet. Four of these words represent four letters, four represent three letters. The numbers represented by these letters are also called “alphabet calculation”, “alphabet order”. The words are: abjad, havwaz, hutti, kalaman, safas, khashat, sakhaz, zazzag’. It is a mistake to think that these words mean nothing. These are important factors for memorizing the alphabet, the table, memorizing the mathematical numbers represented by the letters, multiplying numbers, and deriving history from it. Letter numbering was said to exist in Phoenician-Aramaic alphabet in ancient times (“National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan”). In Uzbek literature, abjad and jimal calculations were also used in writing secret letters. Sharafuddin Ali Yazdi explains that the author Amir Temur’s 71 years of life is expressed in the letters “Alif, lom,

mim” in the work “Zafarnama” and says: “This is one of the great surahs of the Qur’an”.

What is the reason and wisdom of expressing important historical events with special words and phrases through poetic art? Of course, it is not easy to remember the necessary dates and numbers for centuries and years. Therefore, through special words and phrases, the history of important events is ensured to be passed down from generation to generation. Along with all classical writers, Zahiruddin Muhammad Babur also used this art appropriately. Indeed, the secrets of history at the heart of letters are a world of knowledge that enriches thinking.

Babur is an all-round scholar and always worked on himself. He was never free from learning and research. It is necessary to teach these qualities to our current youth. He was interested in many fields and achieved many achievements in this field. Interest in Linguistics: Babur was fluent in many languages of his time. He spoke and wrote fluently in Persian, Turkish, Mongolian and Arabic languages. Similarly, Babur was also interested in learning the Hindi language and created some works related to this language.

Naturalism: Babur’s work “Boburnoma” contains extensive images of natural landscapes, flora and fauna. He wrote down in detail the natural beauties he saw during his travels, which shows his deep appreciation for nature.

Love for Gardening: Babur was very interested in gardening. He ordered the creation of several beautiful gardens in India, including those in Agra and Delhi. His love for horticulture can be seen in Ferghana Valley and Kabul, where he paid special attention to planting his favorite flowers and fruit trees.

Love for Music: Babur was very fond of music and knew how to play the rubab himself. He also participated in the creation of musical works and was in close contact with famous musicians of his time.

Personal Struggles: In Baburnoma, Babur writes openly about his personal feelings, difficulties and inner struggles. This is a rare feature in the historical records of medieval rulers. He also writes about his addiction to alcohol and his subsequent decision to quit.

Contribution to Literature: Babur interacted with influential writers of his time and contributed to the development of literature. He himself wrote a number of poems and ghazals.

Military Strategy and Innovations: Babur was known not only for his bravery on the battlefield but also for his military strategies and innovations. At the Battle of Panipat, he demonstrated his tactical skills, including the effective use of cannon and cannon.

Babur Mirza is known for his versatility, literary legacy and role in Indian history. His work “Boburnoma” is valued not only as a historical source, but also as a literary and cultural heritage.

DISCUSSION.

In our country today, there are ample opportunities for the development of these areas.

The decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, adopted on January 25, 2023, “On the wide celebration of the 540th anniversary of the birth of the great poet and scientist, famous statesman Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur” is a huge event with a logical basis in the spiritual life of our country. It’s done.

As stated in the President’s decision, **“Today, when our beloved Motherland is entering a new stage of national development - the Third Renaissance period, fundamental changes are taking place in all aspects of our lives, the in-depth study and popularization of Babur Mirza’s priceless heritage is becoming even more important”** - he emphasized. The decision is extremely important due to the depth and comprehensiveness of its content. Because we are celebrating the happy birthday of our great and unique poet and great grandfather, based on the Program personally approved by our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev - in our country and on a global scale in a systematic manner and on a large scale.

In the years of independence, attention to the comprehensive study of the rich spiritual and educational heritage of our thinker grandfathers has increased. Including this, the opportunities for deep analysis and research of Babur’s creativity have expanded tremendously. In the past period, “Boburnoma”, “Mubayyin” legal work, Babur’s poetry collection were repeatedly published. Books and pamphlets, scientific and popular articles dedicated to the interpretation of these works are published regularly.

Indeed, in the following years, huge statues of Babur Mirza were erected in the cities of Tashkent and Andijan, and the international public fund named after Babur and the book museum “Babur and World Culture” operated by him are operating in the city of Andijan, where he was born and grew up “Babur encyclopedia”, “Babur Kuliyyot”, “Babur. Baburidiy. Bibliography”. The publication of important works called “Bibliography” and the creation of the magazine “Babur and the World” were recognized as a great event in our cultural life.

At the same time, this decision of our President is closely related to the declaration of 2023 - the year of attention to people and quality education in our country. Why, the issue of incorporating the most important aspects of learning the

creative heritage of Babur Mirza into the content of higher educational institutions and school education programs was defined as an urgent task by the head of our state.

This, in turn, opens more smooth ways to comprehensively study the sensitive books of Babur, in particular, “Baburnoma”, “Devon”, “Aruz Risola”, “Risolai Volidiyya”, “Mubayyin”. The most important thing is to present these rare works to readers and students with various descriptions and comments, to find out the core of their still undiscovered meanings.

Here, first of all, we will talk about the fact that Zahiriddin Babur’s shah and poetry were also engaged in the science of jurisprudence, in modern terms, jurisprudence, and he created an important work called “Mubayyin” on this topic. This book, written by Babur Mirza in the last years of his life, i.e. in 1521, for his sons Humayun Mirza and Kamran Mirza, is a large work explaining the basics of Islam and jurisprudence, including faith, salat (prayer), zakat, consists of five parts devoted to issues of Sawm (fasting) and Hajj.

“Hidaya” by Babur Burkhaniddin Marginani, “al-Jami’ as-Sahih” by Imam Bukhari, “Tawheed” by Imam Moturidi, “Rashahot ain al-hayat” by Fakhriddin Ali Safi, “Siroj ul-Muslimin” by Alisher Navai and other famous muhaddis, studied the works of jurists and thinkers carefully.

The scientific and creative heritage of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur is a priceless treasure, of great historical and scientific importance. Especially, his creativity as a king, his great contribution to the development of science, and his fame as a poet and creator are known and popular all over the world. A compatriot fills the heart with pride.

CONCLUSION.

Mr. Fritz Wuertle’s “Tiger’s Lament” contains the following unique sentences. Umarshaikh Mirza’s letter to his son Zahiruddin Muhammad Babur is in sync with our days:

“My son, God bless you! Listen to what your father says. You know I love peace because a peaceful country is a happy country. I believe in the loyalty of the Ahxi people. If you have something to say to me, always remember: whoever wants to build a house that will stand the test of time, should lay the bricks correctly, and not prepare the mixture in front of the oppressed people! Remember what is written in our holy book: God did not create the Earth and the sky for us to have fun! Always listen to the advice of experienced and wise people, do not ignore them lightly. However, not everyone who gives advice is considered an expert. And you are my son and heir, you are young, brave, always be smart and prudent.

He heard the roar of a tiger from Andijan while standing in the distant Austrian land, added his love and honor, and wrote a beautiful book about the life of our great ancestor and left us a legacy. We pay our respects to those who have contributed immensely .

As a socio-historical phenomenon, the scientific worldview always develops on the basis of inheritance. The outlook of each historical period is unique, and it is important to study the reasons for which doctrines were developed in this period, and how they came into existence. So, in order to think in a new way in society, it is necessary to know the past. Because a new way of thinking arises when studying the heritage of ancestors. Along with modern knowledge, studying the scientific and spiritual heritage of our great ancestors, including Babur, is important in educating young people.

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